

GPU-ACCELERATED FFV1 ENCODING IS HERE – A CASE STUDY USING TEMPORAL FOR DURABLE EXECUTION

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Abstract – GPU-based video encoding is widely available, efficient, and performant, but it has not been adopted in Digital Preservation tooling due to a lack of support for preservation codecs and a quality deficit when working with more common consumer codecs. Recently it has become possible to encode preservation-standard FFV1 video in *ffmpeg* using a GPU, which effectively addresses all previously-existing limitations of this approach. This short paper frames the current state of the art as well as why this development is so potentially useful, and provides a case study of using GPU-accelerated FFV1 encoding with Temporal, a Durable Execution platform that can enable further scaling.

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I. INTRODUCTION

GPU-accelerated video decoding has been widely available in consumer hardware since about 2009 — it roughly coincided with the popularization of modern smartphones. It is dramatically more efficient than CPU-based encoding and decoding, providing much better battery life when e.g. watching YouTube on a mobile device, and yet it has seldom been used in production-scale encoding workflows. The reason for this is straightforward: CPU encoders generally produce higher quality files at lower bitrates. If you are Netflix (or, alternately, MoMA), the quality and size of the file that will live

forever on your server, along with the amount of network bandwidth required to serve it to thousands of viewers, is dramatically more important than the time and energy it takes to encode the video in the first place.

Partly, this is because GPU encoders and decoders typically use a dedicated fixed-function hardware block contained in the GPU, rather than the programmable shader hardware that is used for 3D rendering and other functionality. This fixed-function block is hardcoded into the GPU at manufacture time, and usually runs behind the state of the art in CPU encoders; also, the most popular CPU encoders (such as x264) are GPL licensed and cannot necessarily be used as-is by GPU vendors. This is also why GPU-based encoding is conversely quite popular within livestreaming software such as OBS, and why Twitch streamers are able to broadcast video while simultaneously using their hardware to do something computationally taxing like playing a video game; a Twitch stream is generally not archived in perpetuity, and realtime encoding with no performance penalty is more important in this context anyway.

Consequently no one has been much interested in the use of GPU encoders in digital preservation.

Because modern GPUs are, in pure computational terms, anywhere from 5-50x as powerful as the CPUs they run alongside, GPU encoding is much, much quicker than CPU encoding.

However, the set of codecs that are widely available in consumer GPUs is generally limited to popular consumer video formats — *MPEG2, h.264, h.265, VP9, AV1* — meaning that they would at best be useful for creating access derivatives, e.g. at a variety of different resolutions for bandwidth-limited environments. Most GLAM content management systems have not prioritized automating this type of feature development, in part because it was not possible to use preservation-preferred codecs such as *FFV1* [1,2] with GPU acceleration, and therefore not worth the investment. This may now change.

II. THE FFV1 VULKAN ENCODER

The open source *ffmpeg* software is used by virtually everyone in every industry that has to build any kind of video encoding or decoding solution, and is well known to the iPres community [3]. Thanks to the work of the *ffmpeg* developers, it has recently become possible to develop new GPU-based encoders that, rather than directly using the fixed-function video block of the GPU, instead run on the programmable shader hardware using the *Vulkan* low-level graphics API. This means that GPU encoders can both a) be improved in software and b) provide support for less commercially popular codecs which GPU manufacturers are not motivated to include. Not coincidentally, one of the first implementations of a *Vulkan*-based GPU codec to be added to *ffmpeg* is an *FFV1* encoder [4].

This presents an opportunity for huge gains in encoding efficiency using consumer hardware in ways that are compatible with digital preservation community goals; it should be possible to perform archival time-based media encodes at a dramatically greater scale than before. Furthermore, because *FFV1* is a lossless codec, it should not display the slightly poorer visual results that are typical of hardware encodes using *h.264* or *h.265* compared with CPU-based encoders at the same bitrate.

In fact, the improvement in throughput should be so significant that it presents the need for at-scale workflow management tooling, to handle potentially many concurrent encodes. This paper will provide findings from using *Temporal*, an open-source durable execution platform, with *Nvidia* hardware-accelerated *FFV1* encoding in *ffmpeg*.

III. A CASE STUDY USING TEMPORAL

Durable Execution is a way of orchestrating state persistence and implementing error handling with automatic recovery, to avoid having to spend unnecessary developer time on coding around infrastructure nuances, failures, or edge cases. *Temporal*, which originated Durable Execution, is a commercial open-source platform that provides SDKs for most popular languages. It abstracts away the complexity of building scalable distributed systems.

Durable Execution is a particularly useful abstraction for modeling and orchestrating data processing steps, which describes most digital preservation ingestion workflows [5]. A sample *Temporal* Workflow, written in *Go*, that was used as the basis for this research can be accessed at <https://github.com/temporal-community/temporal-ffmpeg-pipeline>. It uses *stdout* redirection from *ffmpeg* to create observability hooks.

The following *ffmpeg* syntax [6] was used as part of a *Temporal* Workflow to evaluate the new *FFV1* encoder:

```
ffmpeg \
-init_hw_device vulkan=vk:0 \
-hwaccel vulkan -
hwaccel_output_format vulkan \
-hwaccel_device vk -
filter_hw_device vk \
-loglevel info \
-fflags +genpts \
-i 'sample-input.mp4' \
-vf
"bwdif_vulkan,libplacebo=format=y
uv420p" \
-c:v ffv1_vulkan \
-level:v 4 -strict -2 -coder:v 2
-context:v 1 \
-c:a libfdk_aac -b:a 256k -ar
48000 -ac 2 \
```



```
-map "0:v" -map "0:a" \
-max_delay 5000000 -
max_muxing_queue_size 8192 -
max_interleave_delta 0 \

-async_depth 1

-flags -global_header+cgop \

-y -f matroska "output_ffv1.mkv"
```

That produced results with an average speed of about 7.91x realtime on a 24fps, 1080p source file, using an Nvidia RTX 4090:

```
frame= 3102 fps=198 q=-0.0 Lsize=
71942KiB time=00:02:04.12
bitrate=4748.2kbits/s speed=7.91x
```

Notably, the GPU itself only showed a maximum utilization of about 40% during this workflow, and no other part of the hardware was observably bottlenecked, suggesting that this early Vulkan encoder can still become more mature. That also means that the results from using a 4090 should be comparable in the future to using a 4070 — a less powerful GPU — at 100% utilization.

FFV1 encoding on the CPU is known to be “always slower than real time,” with one user citing a typical speed of 6-8 FPS on a “new machine” [7]. This machine can be conservatively assumed to use a CPU with a TDP of about 100 watts, which is average for a modern desktop computer built for work. A 4070 GPU uses slightly less than 200 watts by itself, so if it performs about 24x as quickly as the CPU implementation and does not tax the CPU much during the encoding process, that is an approximate efficiency improvement of 12x, not to mention the time savings.

IV. DISCUSSION

In the view of the author, the only reason that a solution like the one presented here should *not* be of widespread interest to the digital preservation community is because few of its members have a real, pressing need to accelerate their time-based media encoding beyond a boutique scale. This is not a criticism, but a statement of fact — of the already small set of FFV1 users, the number of them who can

justify significant hardware investment to go as fast and as far as possible is smaller still.

Furthermore, the field has historically been skeptical of consolidating or vendorizing the subset of institutions that do perform this work at (relative) scale, for cultural and budgetary reasons, making it challenging to seriously advocate for the work to be done at a level that is at least conversant with commercial streaming platforms, even outside of hyperscale-tier cloud providers. If this does not change, it may become a liability, as it has negative implications for professionalization, service delivery, and mutual intelligibility with industry, as well as other open-source video encoding communities such as the *Demuxed* conference.

The implications for energy consumption are also far from negligible.

While the FFV1 encoder in ffmpeg is still relatively new and requires some experimental feature flags, all the building blocks are now in place to drive adoption. Likewise, while Temporal is not yet widely known to the digital preservation community, being open source means it can be quickly configured locally using the available code samples. Reliably queueing and parallelizing these jobs across different hardware configurations will be a necessity for outrunning format obsolescence.

V. CONCLUSION

FFV1 Vulkan encoding support in ffmpeg is an opportunity for the digital preservation community to take hardware scaling more seriously, and Temporal is a good way to architect for that scale. By standardizing on more robust, performant solutions, we should be able to create a virtuous cycle of higher throughput and lower energy consumption in encoding workflows.

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